

FRANCISCAN FRATERNITY OF HOPE

FOUNDATIONAL DOCUMENT

Official document of the Franciscan Fraternity Franciscan of Hope

"Spes nostra, pax et fraternitas."

In the hope of the Gospel, peace and fraternity

Lord Jesus,
may Your Hope be our strength,
our school of trust,
and our light along the way.
Make us brothers and sisters to all,
sowers of hope,
and witnesses of Your humble love.
Amen.

Foundational Document

Franciscan Fraternity of Hope

In the name of God, the source of all hope, and following in the footsteps of our brother Saint Francis of Assisi and our sister Saint Clare, this fraternity is born as a small shoot of the Gospel offered to the Church and to the world.

The Lord has placed in my heart the desire to live and proclaim Christian hope through simplicity, prayer, and fraternity. This call—received in silence and discerned with humility—has become a shared path with brothers who, like me, seek to follow Christ poor and crucified, trusting fully in the action of the Spirit.

The Franciscans of Hope arise to be a sign of peace, minority, and mercy. We desire to live fraternity as a gift, prayer as a place of encounter with God, and mission as humble service. Our vocation is simple: to be a presence of hope wherever life becomes fragile, where faith grows weak, or where the human heart longs for consolation.

This fraternity does not originate from a human project but from an inspiration the Lord has wished to give. For this reason, from its beginning, we offer it to the Church with a spirit of communion and availability. We desire to walk always in fidelity to the Gospel and to the Franciscan charism that sustains us.

As founder and first Minister Custos, I receive this service not as an honour but as a responsibility entrusted by God. I exercise it with gratitude, with reverent fear, and with the certainty that the fraternity belongs to the Lord, not to those of us who form it. My desire is to safeguard this charism, accompany the brothers, and ensure that the fraternity remains faithful to its identity and mission.

I invite all who feel called to this path to live fraternity with joy, to cultivate contemplative prayer, to embrace minority, and to proclaim hope with their lives before their words. May each brother be a witness of God's goodness and a sower of peace.

I entrust this project to the intercession of the Virgin Mary, Mother of Hope, and of Saint Francis of Assisi and Saint Clare, that they may teach us to live with a heart that is poor, free, and filled with God.

Br. +Mario
Minister Custos
Franciscans of Hope